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**PRODUCTION AND EVALUATION OF CAKE FROM BLENDS OF WHEAT AND PUMPKIN
FLOUR SWEETENED WITH DATE PALM**

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ABSTRACT

Flour was produced from pumpkin flesh and the flour was mixed with wheat flour at various ratios to make wheat and pumpkin composite flour. Cake was then produced from the composite flours sweetened with date palm. The proximate and sensory evaluation of the cake was determined. It was found out that the protein content ranges from 8.00% to 15.45%, and the fat varies from 7.32% to 12.51%. ash content ranges from 1.15% to 1.45%, the moisture content varies from 8.81% to 11.78% and the carbohydrate content ranges from 54.44% to 63.97%. the sensory evaluation carried out indicates that there are significant differences at the (0 0.05) level in all the sensory attributes determined. All the cake samples were acceptable to the panelist although the panelist showed more preference for the cake produced from the blends of 70% wheat flour and 30% pumpkin flour sweetened with date palm to the rest of the samples. This suggests that pumpkin flour can be incorporated into wheat flour up to 30% level to produce cake without any adverse changes in the sensory attributes of the cake.

Keywords: Cake, Date Palm, Pumpkin Flour, Wheat Flour

INTRODUCTION

The rise in health consciousness among consumers has led to an increased demand for functional foods those that provide additional health benefits beyond basic nutrition. Functional foods often incorporate nutrient-dense ingredients that offer specific health benefits. Search for a better diet has brought about so many changes in consumer trends because of the high rates of chronic diseases, such as diabetes, obesity and celiac disease. There have been increases in the demands for healthier pastries that are low in sugar, fat, cholesterol and calories in general and contain health promoting components, such as protein, unsaturated fatty acids and fiber. Cakes are convenient food products which are usually sweet, often baked and prepared from flour, sugar, shortening, baking powder, eggs and other flavour essences as principal ingredients. According to Saeed *et al.* (2021), due to their low cost, extended freshness, and diverse flavour profiles, bakery items such as bread, biscuits, cookies, and cakes are consistently popular among consumers of all age groups. Cakes, typically made with wheat flour, can also include flours from various fruits, vegetables, legumes, roots, and grains to enhance variety and consumer appeal.

Pumpkin is a genus of herbaceous vines belonging to the family of *Cucurbitaceae* which includes other crops such as cucumber, watermelon, gourds, squash and cantaloupes (Adubofuor *et al.*, 2018; Apostol *et al.*, 2020). According to Adubofuor *et al.*, (2018), pumpkins exist in different varieties and they are categorized according to their shape and stem system. This includes *Cucurbita pepo*, *Cucurbita moschata*, *Cucurbita maxima* and *Cucurbita mixta*. Pumpkin offers extensive potential for diversification in food processing and culinary application, which create a wide range of products including jams, pickles, beverages, candies, baked goods, confectioneries, pies, biscuits, and breads, as well as desserts, puddings, soups, and drinks, while also being prominently featured in festivals and agricultural exhibitions worldwide (Mala *et al.*, 2018; Apostol *et al.*, 2020).

Date palm fruit (*Phoenix dactylifera*) locally known as "debino" in the Hausa language from the family of Aracaceae, is a known fruit for its sugary taste. The fruit is a drupe in which the outer fleshy part consists of the pulp and the pericarp surrounding a shell of hard endocarp with the seed inside. According to Dada *et al.* (2012), date palm is mostly produced in the Northern part of Nigeria. The North has 79.10% of cultivable land in Nigeria, date palm fruits consist of more than 70% sugar mainly glucose and fructose. It is high in energy value thus making it an ideal replacement for sugar (sucrose) in the cookie recipe (El Hadrami and Al-Khayri, 2012). It is also of great nutritional benefit because it reduces the risk of increasing the blood sugar level of diabetic patients. Several researchers have done pumpkin-fortified and/or -enriched snacks, which include Apostol *et al.* (2018), Mala *et al.* (2018), Joy *et al.* (2021), Saeed *et al.* (2021), and Waryat *et al.* (2023). However, literature is scarce on the production and evaluation of cake from blends of wheat and pumpkin flour sweetened with date palm. This study aims to evaluate the effect of composite flour on the nutritional, functional and sensory evaluation of wheat-pumpkin cake. The incorporation of pumpkin flour in baked goods not only enhances the nutritional value but also provides a unique flavour profile. Understanding the impact of composite flour on cake quality can provide valuable insights for developing healthier and more appealing bakery products. Furthermore, utilising date palm as a sweetener can offer potential health benefits due to its natural sugars and antioxidants. By exploring the combination of these ingredients, this study aims to contribute to the development of innovative and nutritious bakery products that cater to consumer preferences for healthier options.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The raw materials used for this work were been purchased from the By-pass market in Jimeta Adamawa state (wheat flour, pumpkin and date palm). The analysis was carried out in the department of Food Science and Technology, Food analysis Laboratory Modibbo Adama University Yola and Federal Polytechnic, Mubi in the Department of food science and Technology.

Sample Preparation

Pumpkin flour preparation

Figure 1 shows the modified flowchart for producing pumpkin flour in accordance with Mepba *et al.* (2007)'s method. The pumpkin will be washed, peeled and cleaned of seed and fibrous core, cut into thin slices of about 1 cm thickness, then washed in cold water and blanched (1.25% NaHSO₃ solution at 80°C for 10 min). The slices were dehydrated under the sun for 5 days, the dried pumpkin slices were milled into flour using an attrition mill. The flour obtained was sieved through a 250-um aperture sieved and packed in a two-ply medium density (0.926 – 0.949g/cc) polythene Ziploc bag.

Figure 1: Pumpkin flour production

Date flour preparation

As illustrated in Figure 2, the date palm fruits undergo the following process: initial cleaning and sorting to remove damaged fruits, washing, de-seeding, sun-drying on stainless steel trays for three days, milling into flour using an attrition mill, sieving through a 250- μ m aperture sieve, and packaging in two-ply medium-density (0.926-0.949 g/cc) polythene Ziploc bags.

Preparation of Composite Flour and Wheat-pumpkin Cake Production

The wheat flour is labelled “W” and the pumpkin flour “P” for ease of identification. The two flours were mixed at 90:10, 80:20, 70:30, 60:40 and 100:00 (Table 1). The process involved in the production of the wheat-pumpkin cake is depicted in Figure 3, involving a step-by-step flowchart for the process, from ingredient weighing to storage.

Table 1: Formulation Ratio for the wheat and pumpkin composite flour blends

Samples	Wheat flour (%)	Pumpkin flour (%)
A	90	10
B	80	20
C	70	30
D	60	40
E	100	00

Figure 2: Production of date palm flour

Proximate Analysis

The proximate composition (ash content, protein content, moisture content, crude fibre and crude fat) of the cake was carried out by the methods recommended by the Association of Analytical Chemists AOAC (2010), while the total carbohydrates were calculated by difference.

Functional Properties

Bulk Density (BD)

Bulk density was determined by the method described by Maninder *et al.* (2007) and Tangsrianugul *et al.* (2019). The samples were filled gently into 10 mL graduated cylinders, and the bottoms of the cylinders were tapped gently on a laboratory bench until there was no more diminution of the sample level at the 10ml mark. The weight of the sample was taken and bulk density calculated as weight per unit volume.

$$\text{Bulk density (g/mL)} = \frac{\text{weight of sample (g)}}{\text{Vol.of sample (mL)}} \quad (1)$$

Figure 3: The production of the wheat-pumpkin cake

Water Absorption Capacity (WAC)

The water absorption capacity was performed by employing the method described by Joy *et al.* (2021). One gram of sample (W_0) was weighed into a pre-weighed 15 mL centrifuge tubes (W_1). 10 mL of distilled water was added and mixed using a vortex at the highest speed for 2 minutes. After the mixture was thoroughly wetted, the samples were allowed to stand at room temperature for 30 minutes, and then centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 25 minutes at 20°C. The supernatant was decanted and the centrifuge tube containing sediment was weighed (W_2). Water Absorption capacity (grams of water per gram of sample) was calculated as:

$$WAC = \frac{(W_2 - W_1)}{W_0} \tag{2}$$

Where: WAC = water absorption capacity, W_0 = weight of the dry sample (g), W_1 = weight of the tube plus the dry sample (g), W_2 = weight of the tube plus the sediment (g).

Least Gelation Concentration (LGC)

The least gelation concentration (LGC) was determined using the method described by Onitilo *et al.* (2007). Eight suspensions (6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, and 20% w/v) in 5 ml of distilled water were prepared in test tubes. The test tubes containing the suspensions were heated in a boiling water bath (Thelco, Model 83, USA) for 1 hour. The tubes and their contents were then rapidly cooled under running cold water and further cooled for 2 hours at 4°C. Next, the tubes were

inverted to check if the contents would fall or slip off. The least gelation concentration was identified as the concentration at which the sample from the inverted test tube did not fall or slip off.

Swelling Capacity (SC)

A 100 mL graduated cylinder was filled with the sample to the 10 mL mark; distilled water was added to give a total volume of 50 mL, and the top of the graduated cylinder was tightly covered and mixed by inverting the cylinder. The suspension was inverted again after 2 minutes and left to stand for a further 8 minutes; the volume occupied by the sample was taken after the 8th min (Chandra *et al.*, 2015).

Sensory Evaluation

The sensory evaluation of the cakes was by the method of Mala *et al.* (2018). A 10-man semi-trained panelist group who were neither sick nor allergic to any of the raw materials were used to evaluate the taste, appearance, colour, mouthfeel and general acceptability of the cakes using a 9-point hedonic scale (9 = liked extremely, 8 = liked very much, 7 = liked, 6 = liked mildly, 5 = neither liked nor disliked, 4 = disliked mildly, 3 = disliked, 2 = disliked very much and 1 = disliked extremely).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Proximate composition of cake produced from wheat-pumpkin composite flour

Table 2 shows the proximate composition of cake produced from the blends of wheat and pumpkin flour. The protein contents ranges from 8.00% to 15.45%, fat (7.32 - 12.54%), ash (1.14 – 1.45%), fibre (3.34 – 9.72%), moisture (8.81 – 11.78%), and carbohydrates (54.44 – 63.97%), respectively.

The optimum protein content was recorded for sample A (15.45%), produced from 100% wheat flour while the minimum protein content was observed in sample E (8.00%) produced from 60% wheat and 40% pumpkin flour. The variation in protein content of the cake could be attributed to the higher protein concentration in wheat flour relative to pumpkin flour, which has a lower protein content and dilutes the overall protein level in the blended formulation. Also, the protein content appears to decrease with an increase in the amount of pumpkin flour inclusion. This result contradicts the findings of Apostol *et al.* (2020), that the incorporation of pumpkin powder into wheat flour results in an increase of the protein content of the dough. It's crucial to keep in mind that other elements like recipe formulation and processing techniques may also have an impact on the protein content of the finished product. Further research is needed to determine the optimal blend ratio for maximizing protein content in cakes made with wheat and pumpkin flour.

The maximum fat of the cake was observed in sample A (12.54%), whereas the minimum was recorded in sample E (7.32%) (Table 2). The increment in the fat content of sample A could be attributed to the presence of high fat content in wheat flour compared to pumpkin flour, which has a higher water and fiber content but lower fat content. Similar trend as the protein content was also observed in the fat content, with an increase in fat content of the cake with a decrease in pumpkin flour content. This result contradicts the findings of Saeed *et al.* (2021), that an increase in the ratio of pumpkin flour results in an increase in the fat content of cookies. According to Table 2, the cake obtained its minimum ash content in sample A (1.14%); however, the maximum ash content for the cake was recorded in sample E (1.45%). Ubbor *et al.* (2022) claim that it is possible to determine the mineral content of food by measuring its ash content, which serves as the last vestige of the

inorganic residue. The variation in the ash content of the cake may be due to the higher mineral content in pumpkin flour, which increases the overall ash content when incorporated into the formulation. This result corroborates with the findings of Apostol et al. (2020) that increasing the ratio of substitution of pumpkin flour results in an increase in the ash content of the dough. Similarly, Saeed et al. (2021) reported an increase in the ash content of cookies with an increase in the pumpkin's flour ratio. These results suggest that the use of pumpkin flour in baked goods can significantly impact the ash content, highlighting the importance of considering this factor in recipe formulation.

The fibre content was observed to attain its maximum value in sample E (9.72%). Dietary fiber promotes gastrointestinal and heart health while reducing blood cholesterol and slowing glucose absorption, which helps regulate blood sugar levels. The increase in the fibre content of sample E compared to sample B could be attributed to lower fiber concentration in wheat flour relative to pumpkin flour, leading to a higher overall fiber content with a greater proportion of pumpkin flour. This result aligns with the findings of McArthur-Floyd and Brako (2024); the increase in the ratio of pumpkin flour results in an increase in the fibre content of pumpkin formulated cookies. The moisture content of the cake ranges between 8.81 – 11.78%, with the highest moisture content recorded for sample B, while the least was measured for sample A (Table 2). The variation in moisture content of the cake may be due to the inherent higher water-holding capacity of pumpkin flour, which contributes more moisture to the final product. This result aligns with the findings of Waryat *et al.* (2023) that an increase in pumpkin flour ratio decrease the moisture content of the cake due to lower pumpkin flour hygroscopic properties compared to wheat flour. As illustrated in Table 2, the optimum carbohydrate content was recorded for sample E (63.97). The variation in the carbohydrate content of the cake could be attributed to the presence of more starch granules in pumpkin flour than wheat flour, thereby leading to a higher carbohydrate content compared to the control cake. This result corroborates with the findings of Waryat *et al.* (2023), who reported an increase in the carbohydrate content of cake with increase in the ratio of pumpkin flour.

Table 2: Proximate composition of wheat-pumpkins cake (%)

Sample	Protein	Fat	Ash	Fibre	Moisture	Carbohydrate
A	15.45 ^a ±1.18	12.54 ^a ±0.08	1.14 ^e ±0.19	7.62 ^b ±0.24	8.81 ^a ±2.70	54.44 ^c ±0.09
B	10.45 ^b ±0.05	10.48 ^b ±0.05	1.20 ^c ±0.35	3.34 ^b ±0.01	11.78 ^b ±1.42	62.75 ^b ±0.11
C	9.32 ^c ±1.47	9.30 ^c ±0.05	1.33 ^b ±0.05	5.78 ^b ±0.05	11.60 ^b ±0.52	62.67 ^b ±0.07
D	8.51 ^d ±1.03	8.36 ^d ±0.05	1.40 ^a ±0.21	7.83 ^a ±0.06	10.74 ^c ±0.07	63.16 ^a ±0.12
E	8.00 ^e ±1.34	7.32 ^e ±0.11	1.45 ^c ±0.11	9.72 ^c ±0.11	9.54 ^d ±0.63	63.97 ^a ±0.06

Key: all mean scores with the same superscript in the same column are not significantly different at ($0 \leq 0.05$) level. A= 100% wheat flour: 0.00% pumpkin flour; B= 90% wheat flour: 10% pumpkin flour; C= 80% wheat flour: 20% pumpkin flour; D= 70% wheat flour: 30% pumpkin flour; E= 60% wheat flour: 40% pumpkin flour.

Functional Properties of cake produced from wheat-pumpkin composite flour

The functional properties of the wheat-pumpkin cake are depicted in Table 3, the functional properties ranged between 1.04 and 2.65 ml/g for water absorption capacity (WAC), bulk density (0.58 – 0.61 g/ml), least gelation concentration (8.50 – 12.50%), and swelling capacity (53.71 – 77.91%). The optimum WAC was recorded in sample E (2.65 ml/g), whereas the minimum was obtained in sample A (1.04). The difference in WAC could be attributed to the higher fiber content and different starch properties of pumpkin flour, which enhance water retention compared to wheat flour. This result aligns with

the study of Joy *et al.* (2021), which found that an increase in pumpkin flour ratio increases the water absorption capacity of cake due to the high fiber content of pumpkin flour. The highest bulk density was observed in sample E (0.61 g/ml); the bulk density was observed to increase with an increase in the inclusion of pumpkin flour. In a study highlighted by Joy *et al.* (2021), bulk density determined by the particle size and density of flour, is a critical parameter for efficient handling, processing, and packaging operations in food manufacturing. The variation in the bulk density could be associated with increasing pumpkin flour is attributed to the higher porosity and lower packing efficiency of the pumpkin flour matrix compared to the denser wheat flour structure. This result corroborates with the findings of Adubofuor *et al.* (2018), that an increase in the pumpkin flour increases the bulk density of pumpkin-wheat composite flour for bread. However, the results obtained for this study were lower compared to those reported by Toan *et al.* (2018) 0.69 -0.91 g/cm³ for pumpkin biscuit.

The maximum least gelation concentration (LGC) for the wheat-pumpkin cake was obtained in samples D and E (12.50%). The LGC was observed to increase down the line with an increase in pumpkin flour. The variation in the LGC in the samples could be attributed to the higher fiber and protein content of pumpkin flour, which promotes stronger protein-protein interactions and enhanced water-holding capacity, facilitating gel formation at lower concentrations compared to wheat flour alone. This result is consistent with the findings of Joy *et al.* (2021), that the LGC increases with an increase in pumpkin flour. Also, the results fall within the range reported by Joy *et al.* (2021) 8.50 – 16.50% for pumpkin pulp flour cake. The swelling capacity is the ability of a product to increase in volume through absorption of water. The highest swelling capacity was recorded for sample E, whereas the minimum was obtained for sample A. The swelling capacity was observed to increase across the sample with an increase in pumpkin flour. The variation in the swelling capacity of the cake can be associated with the higher fiber content and altered starch interactions in the pumpkin flour, which enhance water retention and expansion. This result aligns with the findings of Adubufor *et al.* (2018), that higher pumpkin substitution results in an increase in swelling capacity due to amylopectin which is responsible for granule swelling.

Table 3: Functional properties of Wheat /Pumpkin Flour Blends

Sample	WAC (ml/g)	BD (g/ml)	LGC (%)	SC (%)
A	1.04 ± 0.10 ^e	0.58 ± 0.02 ^a	8.50 ± 0.76 ^c	53.71 ± 2.62 ^e
B	1.43 ± 0.18 ^d	0.59 ± 0.01 ^a	10.50 ± 0.71 ^b	58.93 ± 2.52 ^d
C	1.97 ± 0.07 ^c	0.60 ± 0.02 ^a	10.50 ± 0.54 ^b	70.51 ± 1.81 ^c
D	2.43 ± 0.11 ^b	0.60 ± 0.01 ^a	12.50 ± 0.23 ^a	77.18 ± 1.52 ^b
E	2.65 ± 0.15 ^a	0.61 ± 0.01 ^a	12.50 ± 0.72 ^a	77.91 ± 1.65 ^a

Means are ± standard deviation of triplicate analysis. Means within a column that do not share the same letter are significantly different.

WAC = Water Absorption Capacity, BD = Bulk Density, LGC = Least Gelation Concentration, SC = Swelling Capacity. A= 100% wheat flour: 0.00% pumpkin flour; B= 90% wheat flour: 10% pumpkin flour; C= 80% wheat flour: 20% pumpkin flour; D= 70% wheat flour: 30% pumpkin flour; E= 60% wheat flour: 40% pumpkin flour.

Sensory Evaluation of cake produced from wheat-pumpkin composite flour

The sensory evaluation of the cake shown in Table 4 indicate the sample D has the highest value for taste, texture and general acceptability with values of 8.4, 7.7, and 8.1, respectively. The inclusion of pumpkin flour could have contributed to the panelist favouritism for sample D compared to other samples. In terms of taste, this result contradicts the findings of

Adubufor *et al.* (2018), which state that the inclusion of over 25% of pumpkin flour results in less panelist favouritism of pumpkin composite snacks due to the level of secondary metabolites such as anti-nutrients in the pumpkin flour, which results in a bitter taste. In a study highlighted by Waryat *et al.* (2023), the panelist favour muffins with 50% pumpkin inclusion in term of texture and general acceptability. However, percentage below or above 50% such as 25% or 75% were least favoured. Also, in terms of aroma and colour, the panelist favoured sample A. The highest aroma value (7.8) was the highest by the panelist which is described as the most distinct and the most favourable. The colour of the cake was observed to decrease with an increase in the pumpkin flour. This result is in consistent with that of Waryat *et al.* (2023), who reported a decrease in colour rating by panelist with an increase in pumpkin flour. Overall, the study suggests that the optimal percentage of pumpkin inclusion in cake recipes for texture and general acceptability is around 30%. The study also found that the texture of the cake improved with an increase in pumpkin flour up to 30%. This suggests that incorporating pumpkin flour in cake recipes can enhance both texture and overall acceptability among consumers. Further research may be needed to understand the discrepancies in aroma and colour preferences between different studies.

Table 4: sensory evaluation of cake produced from wheat-pumpkin composite flour

Samples	Taste	Aroma	Colour	Texture	General acceptability
A	7.50 ± 0.43 ^b	7.80 ± 0.25 ^{ab}	7.80 ± 0.45 ^a	7.40 ± 0.22 ^{bc}	7.70 ± 1.10 ^b
B	7.60 ± 0.22 ^b	7.20 ± 0.25 ^{bc}	7.50 ± 0.31 ^b	7.60 ± 1.20 ^{ab}	7.40 ± 0.15 ^c
C	7.20 ± 0.25 ^c	7.10 ± 0.23 ^c	7.10 ± 0.23 ^c	7.60 ± 0.22 ^{ab}	7.30 ± 0.22 ^c
D	8.40 ± 0.16 ^a	7.40 ± 0.27 ^a	7.30 ± 0.74 ^{bc}	7.70 ± 1.40 ^a	8.10 ± 0.82 ^a
E	6.30 ± 0.26 ^d	6.80 ± 0.36 ^d	6.80 ± 0.33 ^a	7.30 ± 0.74 ^c	6.50 ± 0.34 ^d

Key: all means scores with the same super script in the same column are not significantly different at ($0 \leq 0.05$) level.

A = 100% wheat flour: 0.00 pumpkin flour; B = 90% wheat flour: 10% pumpkin flour; C = 80% wheat flour: 20% pumpkin flour; D = 70% wheat flour: 30% pumpkin flour; E = 60% wheat flour: 40% pumpkin flour

CONCLUSION

The incorporation of pumpkin flour of different ratios resulted in changes in the nutritional, functional and sensory properties of the cake. This study revealed that pumpkin powder enhances the protein, fat, ash, fibre, carbohydrates and reduces the moisture of the product. Also, the increase in pumpkins flour was concluded to have increased the functional properties of the cake. On the basis of sensory evaluation, the replacement of pumpkin flour at a 30% level was found to improve the taste, texture and general acceptability. Additionally, the sample with 100% wheat was concluded to have influenced the aroma and colour. The substitution higher than 30% has a negative relation to the cake in terms of sensory evaluation. In conclusion, incorporating pumpkin powder into cake recipes cannot only improve the nutritional profile but also enhance the overall sensory experience for consumers. It is recommended to carefully balance the amount of pumpkin flour used to achieve optimal results in terms of taste and texture.

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